

ASSESSMENT OF THE WINDING PATTERN EFFECTS ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF FILAMENT WOUND PIPES BY USING FULL FIELD MEASUREMENTS AND THE EQUILIBRIUM GAP METHOD

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SUMMARY

A filament-winding pipe is tested to identify the local behaviour of the structure, observed by using CCD cameras. An orthotropic variant of the Equilibrium Gap Method is then proposed and applied. The displacement field is used in order to obtain heterogeneities map for establishing a relation between local mechanical properties and the wound pattern.

Keywords: Filament winding, structural tests, full field measurement, Equilibrium Gap Method.

I. INTRODUCTION

Composite structures are heterogeneous structures by constitution. This often leads to variations of mechanical behaviour at different scales which may lead to complex behaviours and modelling. In some cases, e.g., because of a coarse fibrous architecture, the classical homogenisation techniques may not be applicable to get a relevant macroscopic behaviour. On another way, the material can also present singularities due to the process (holes, corner fitting, ply drop off ...) that lead to structural heterogeneities. Additionally, the material may not be studied out of the structure, because of its particular process or geometry. . In the following, we focus on a structure including most of these complexities. The later consists in a filament-wound glass/epoxy composite pipe. This kind of structure is planned to be use by the French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea (IFREMER) for deep water research.

Filament winding is one of the older processes to obtain composite structures. A horizontal CNC machine with three degrees of freedom, which are: axial displacement, mandrel rotation, and radial displacement, is used for this purpose (see Figure 1a). It has a carriage with longitudinal displacements, provided with a roving feed system. Roving is wound on the mandrel which is attached to the machine spindle. Combined axial and rotation displacements produce double helicoidal paths. This kinematics forms a rhomboid shape, which is a classical filament winding pattern (see Figure 1b). A detailed explanation of winding patterns can be found in references [1-2].

Figure 1. a) Filament winding process, b) winding pattern induced by filament winding.

Development of optical methods, as Digital Image Stereo-Correlation (DISC) techniques, allows increasing the understanding of the material behaviour during a mechanical test. Depending on the scale of the measure, it can inform about the “real boundary condition” of the test. On the other hand, it can show some strain field heterogeneities that, in certain cases, can reflect material heterogeneities or damages. This capacity is particularly useful when studying the multi scale behaviour of heterogeneous structures such as composites.

Few inverse methods based on these measures allow estimating these variations, in particular in the case of orthotropic materials. The objective of this paper is to propose an identification procedure to establish a mean macroscopical behaviour and maps of contrasts of rigidities. First, mechanical tests realized on pipes are presented, measures are exploited and commented. Then, a declination for orthotropic materials of Equilibrium Gap Method is proposed. Finally, a first application to flat weaved coupons (reproducing the winding pattern present in the pipes) illustrates the contribution of the method.

II. MECHANICAL TESTS ON PIPE

To characterize mean mechanical properties of filament wound pipes, certain numbers of structural tests are performed on pipes. The studied pipes were produced in particular to study the influence of the winding pattern on the mechanical behaviour of this type of structures [3-4]. However due to the difficulty to create a simple and flat representative coupon taking all the weaving problems, one rather considers that the object of the mechanical studies should be the structure itself (or a representative smaller structure). It seems difficult to realize a flat structure recreating the winding and respecting the physico-chemical properties of the real structure. The considered pipe is constituted by 14 plies of fibreglass of type E presented as a roving of 1200 tex (mainly for economic and supply reasons) and of a resin constituted by a mixture of Araldite LY 5052 and hardener HY 5052.

The thickness obtained is about 4.4 mm, for a length of the useable zone of 280 mm and an internal diameter of 125 mm. The fibres are laid out according to an angle of $\pm 55^\circ$ with regard to the axis of the obtained pipe (see Figure 2a). Furthermore, the winding patterns are stacked along the thickness (same location in one ply and in the following)

to amplify the influence of the winding pattern onto the mechanical properties (see Figure. 2b).

Figure 2. a) Pipe's geometry b) superposition of winding pattern through the thickness.

Structural mechanical tests are carried on these pipes. "Conventional" loadings like tension, torsion and external pressure are applied, but also "combined" loadings such as torsion/bending and traction/bending. All the experiments were instrumented by strain gages glued on the inner face of the tubular structure. In addition to this inboard instrumentation, the strain field measurements are performed with the Digital Image Stereo-Correlation (DISC) technique. This technique is based on Digital Image Correlation (DIC) [9] and stereovision.]. In the following, Vic-3D® software developed and implemented by Correlated Solution Incorporated (CSI) is used. A random speckle pattern is sprayed on the outer surface (white speckle on a black background). Two time-synchronized stereo-rigs (noted A and B) are used in order to get images of the same specimen at two distinct scales: a meso/macro view (typically corresponding to the cell size: stereo-rig A) and a structural view (stereo-rig B) (see figure 7c). The stereo-rig A is composed of two high resolution (1280 x 1024 pixels²) 8-bit CCD Qimaging Retiga synchronized cameras equipped with two 28-70 mm Nikkor lens, and the stereo-rig B is composed of two high resolution (1360 x 1036 pixels²) 8-bit CCD Qimaging Qicam synchronized cameras equipped with two 28-200 mm Tamron lens. Several parameters are involved in the stereocorrelation technique: the subset size S that gives the displacement spatial resolution, the step of the grid of the matched points p , and the size N of the square surface of neighbouring matched points chosen for the strain computation and giving the strain spatial resolution.

Figure 3. a) Multi instrumented test on tubular coupon, b) relative position for areas observed by full field measurements

The subset size S is chosen according to the speckle pattern of the specimen. Indeed a randomly speckle pattern is obtained by projection of spray painting (white speckle on a black background). For the A stereo-rig, S is fixed to $31 \times 31 \text{ px}^2$ and p to 10 px , the image resolution (or magnification, g) is 0.0802 mm/px . With these parameters, the (displacement) spatial resolution is $S \times g = 2.49 \text{ mm}$. For the B stereo-rig, S is fixed to $25 \times 25 \text{ px}^2$ and p to 7 pixels , the image resolution g is 0.183 mm/px . With these values, the (displacement) spatial resolution is $S \times g = 4.57 \text{ mm}$. In the both case, the number of neighbouring matched points chosen for the strain computation is 15, so the strain spatial resolution (size of the “optical gage”) is $N = 15 \times p \text{ px}$, equivalent to an optical gage of $N = 15 \times p \times g \text{ mm}$. This leads the optical gage to be equal to 12 mm (150 px) and 19.2 mm (105 px) respectively for the A and B stereo-rig.

Tensile and torsion tests combined with external pressure in a hyperbaric chamber by IFREMER, give access to all the homogenized mechanical properties (see Table 1). This identification, made from mean strains measured during each mechanical test, is led by a multi-criterion optimization. The pipe is constituted by an orthotropic heterogeneous material, for which orthotropic axes are the axis direction z , the radial direction r and orthoradial one θ . The pipe is then assumed to be made of 14 unidirectional plies (classical laminates theory for a $[\pm 55^\circ]$). A second multi-criterion optimization allows the identifying the ply in plane mechanical properties. A F.E. model of the tubular coupon is built using the later identified properties. The results of the simulations for a set of mechanical tests are finally compared to the experimental values in Tab. 1.

Table 1. Identified results at two scales (left) and measured and computed strains (right)

Macroscopic properties identified	Ply properties identified	Sollicitation case	Strains measured (10^{-6})	Strains F.E. (10^{-6})
$E_z = 9,4$ GPa	$E_1 = 41,4$ GPa	Tensile test	$\epsilon_{zz} = 985$	$\epsilon_{zz} = 933$
$E_\theta = 16,6$ GPa	$E_2 = 9,6$ GPa		$\epsilon_{\theta\theta} = -391$	$\epsilon_{\theta\theta} = -376$
$\nu_{z\theta} = 0,41$ GPa	$\nu_{12} = 0,25$ GPa	Torsion	$\epsilon_{z\theta} = 3950$	$\epsilon_{z\theta} = 3585$
$G_{z\theta} = 9,6$ GPa	$G_{12} = 3,6$ GPa	External pressure	$\epsilon_{zz} = -883$	$\epsilon_{zz} = -905$
			$\epsilon_{\theta\theta} = -2559$	$\epsilon_{\theta\theta} = -2775$

A good agreement is observed between computed and measured strains. This could indicate that the identified ply parameters are relevant at the structural level from the gage point of view. During simple loading tests (torsion and tension), strain fields measured by full field measurements at both scales do not show a strong variability of strain along the surface conventional torsion and tensile test. (see Figure 4a). when the specimen is subjected to a combined tension/bending loading, strain patterns appear. They seem linked to the local winding pattern (see Figures 4b and 4c).

Figure 4. a) Shear strain field measured during a torsion test, b) axial strain field during a test with combination of traction and flexure, c) local radius computed by stereo vision

The measured strain fields indicate that the mechanical macroscopical properties of this kind of structures are probably not homogeneous. They seem to be influenced by the winding pattern due to the filament winding process. An identification procedure of mechanical properties fields from full field measurements seems indeed to be an attractive way to establish the link between local mechanical properties and the local winding pattern.

III. IDENTIFICATION OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES FIELDS USING DISPLACEMENTS FIELDS: THE EQUILIBRIUM GAP METHOD

The recent advances of full field measurements have led to the development of alternative inverse methods exploiting the heterogeneity of measured. In many studies, the authors focus on the assumed homogeneous elastic orthotropic behaviour of

composites, namely, the determination of four parameters. The Finite Element Method Updating (FEMU) for example permits to obtain all mechanical properties of a composite structure using an heterogeneous test. Alternative non-iterative methods exist. One can, for example, use the Virtual Fields Method (VFM). This technique permits to obtain all the set of mean mechanical properties without using any FE Model. Most of these identification methods allows retrieving mean mechanical properties of homogeneous materials. Some of them, as the Equilibrium Gap Method (EGM) [2], are specifically developed to study heterogeneous materials. The EGM basically consists in searching contrasts of rigidities that obey the internal equilibrium for a given displacement field.

3.1 Orthotropic variant of the Equilibrium Gap Method: Finite Difference approach

In the following, one proposes to extend the EGM to orthotropic materials. The material is still decomposed in elementary cells (the behaviour is assumed to be orthotropic and homogeneous in each cell). Nevertheless, one no longer uses a weak form of the equilibrium gap. Rather than a Finite Element approach, a finite difference scheme is used (equilibrium is directly expressed in terms of resultants instead of a minimisation of the strain energy). This choice is compatible with the way the information is assessed and treated in usual DIC softwares. Displacement fields are usually retrieved on a regular uniform grid and strains are generally computed using a finite differences scheme. In addition, this numerical scheme leads to a simple implementation and physical meaning of the method.

Firstly, the equilibrium between adjacent cells is considered. As suggested in [8], but written in a stress formulation, the continuity of the normal stress vector across the interface $\partial\omega$ between two adjacent cells is first addressed by writing the jump condition

$$[\underline{\sigma n}] = \underline{0} \text{ on } \partial\omega \quad (1)$$

At this stage, one can simply express the stresses inside the cells by using the computed strains (from the known displacements) and the rigidities. One can then relate the measured displacements and unknown rigidities of two adjacent cells. For each interface, one obtains two scalar equations (both linear) with respect to the rigidities of the cells. For example, the equation relative to the continuity of the normal component can be written eq (2). $u_{i,j}$ and $v_{i,j}$ are measured horizontal and vertical displacements, and $K_{p(i,j)}$ rigidities for the element numbered i,j .

$$\sum_{p=1}^4 (K_{p(i,j)} \cdot G_p(u_{i,j}, v_{i,j}) - K_{p(i+1,j)} \cdot G_p(u_{i+1,j}, v_{i+1,j})) = 0 \quad (2)$$

To deal with the increasing number of unknowns per element (in comparison with the isotropic case), it is proposed to write additional equations through the equilibrium of inner cells and of inner corner nodes. This leads to a new set of linear equations with respect to unknown moduli. Because the equations simply link the material properties of adjacent cells through the measured displacements, the EGM only gives access to the contrast $\delta_{p(i,j)}$ of the property $K_{p(i,j)}$ in cell (i,j) with respect to an arbitrary reference modulus K_{po} (3).

$$K_{p(i,j)} = K_{p_o} (1 - \delta_{p(i,j)}) \quad (3)$$

The system of linear equations formed is overdetermined (typically by a factor of ca. 1.8 for a grid of 20x20 cells). It is solved by using a conjugate gradient method (an identity preconditioning matrix transforms the system into a square form). When static quantities are known, namely, resultants or moments on boundaries, one may then use a one-step finite element updating method in order to find the reference modulus K_{p_o} .

3.2 Validation using synthetic data

The identification method is validated using displacements fields resulting from FE models. The Region Of Interest (ROI) is meshed with squared elements (Q4-P1). In each element, a set of known rigidities is enforced. These properties vary from an element to another.

Figure 5. a) Biaxial virtual test, b) shear modulus field imposed, c) shear modulus field identified

Computed nodal displacements are used as entry data for the identification method. A set of contrasts maps is obtained for each rigidity. The identified contrasts maps can be compared with imposed ones (see Figure 5). A agreement is observed.

IV. APPLICATION FOR HAND MADE WOVEN PLATES

4.1 Flat coupons and tensile tests

Flat woven tensile coupons are manufactured to reproduce, on a flat form, the typical winding pattern resulting from the filament winding. The idea is to carry on a complete identification procedure on a simpler case study. Filament rovings are placed manually respecting filament orientation of the considered pipe (ie. $\pm 55^\circ$). This procedure allows to obtain plates (see Figure 6a) in which coupons are finally cut. Coupons are made with two plies, symmetrically disposed through the thickness.

The tensile tests performed on these flat coupons are multi instrumented using, in particular, a pair of CCD cameras. A random speckle pattern painted onto the surface (black speckle on a white background) and a Digital Image Stereo Correlation software (ViC3D) allows for retrieving the 3D displacements on the surface (see Figure 6b).

Figure 6. a) Winded plate, b) multi-instrumented tensile tests with CCD cameras

Tensile tests are carried out until fracture. Displacement fields are retrieved at several loading steps. The subset size S is chosen according to the speckle pattern of the specimen. S is fixed to $19 \times 19 \text{ px}^2$ and p to 9 px , the image resolution (or magnification, g) is 0.13 mm/px so the (displacement) spatial resolution is $S \times g = 2.47 \text{ mm}$. The results obtained from the very beginning of the loading confirm phenomena observed for tubular structures: strain fields appear to be heterogeneous ones and seem to have influence by the winding pattern (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. a) Coupon during tensile test, b) and c) horizontal and vertical displacement fields

4.2 Application of the EGM on flat coupons

The EGM is applied to a series of displacement fields measured during tensile tests performed on the flat specimens. The material is assumed to be orthotropic. The orthotropic axes here coincide with the direction of the loading. A plane stress state is assumed. No significant out of plane displacements are noted. Figure 8 presents contrasts maps corresponding to the four rigidities K_1 , K_2 , K_3 and K_4 obtained at the last elastic load step (no significant damage is identified). These contrasts maps can be

compared to the local winding computed by stereovision. The local winding seems to have an influence onto the mechanical behaviour.

Figure 8. a)) Relief due to pattern measured by stereovision; b) contrasts map obtained with the EGM for the rigidities K_1 , K_2 , K_3 and K_4

The tested coupons are certainly not representative of the pipes manufactured by filament winding. In particular the fibre content or the precision of the fibre placement can not be the same. Nevertheless, these simpler case studies illustrate the results that can supply later developments of the identification procedure sketched in this work. The method should be soon be applied to real filament wound pipes

CONCLUSION

The influence of the particular winding pattern onto the mechanical properties of filament winding pipes is investigated. Structural mechanical tests performed on glass/epoxy pipes are presented. The experiments are multi instrumented. Gages are glued on the inner face while Digital Image Stereo Correlation is used to retrieve displacement fields at the outer surface of the specimen. A set of structural tests under simple loadings, ie. tensile, torsion and external pressure, allows identifying “average” mechanical properties at the macroscopic and at the ply scale. Nevertheless, the study of the displacement fields collected when the pipe is subjected to combined loadings demonstrates an influence of the winding pattern on the mechanical response.

An orthotropic variant of the Equilibrium Gap Method is then proposed to establish a link between the macro rigidities and the local architecture. A finite difference scheme is used to find relations between the rigidities of adjacent cells for a given displacement field. The measured displacement fields are then the input of the procedure. One finally gets contrasts maps for the four orthotropic rigidities. The validity of the method is demonstrated through the use of synthetic data.

This EGM variant is finally applied to tensile tests performed on hand made flat woven specimens. These coupons were manufactured to reproduce the particular winding pattern due to the filament winding process. The use of displacement fields measured

during the experiment supplies maps of contrasts of rigidities. The obtained results of this simpler case study confirm the influence of the weaving pattern on local mechanical properties. The procedure should soon be extended to the 3D case in order to study the actual pipes.

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